

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On Univalent Functions with Negative Coefficients Defined by Mittag-Leffler Function

Pasunoori Srinivasulu¹ and V. Srinivas²

¹Department of Mathematics, Rajeev Gandhi university of knowledge technologies, IIIT, Basar, Nirmal-504 107. T.S. India.

²Department of Mathematics, Dr. B.R. Ambedkar Open University, Hyderabad -500033. T.S. India.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: P. Srinivasulu (srinivasrgukt1203@gmail.com)

Abstract

In this paper, we present and carefully examine a new subclass of analytic functions characterized by a differential operator. Moreover, we derive coefficient estimates, extreme points, starlikeness, and radii of close-to-convexity for the aforementioned class. Furthermore, we investigate the integral means inequalities thereof.

Keywords: analytic functions; univalent functions; Mittag-Leffler function; coefficient bounds; starlike; distortion.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 30C45

1 Introduction

Let A denote the class of analytic functions f defined on the unit disk $U = \{z : |z| < 1\}$ with normalization $f(0) = 0$ and $f'(0) = 1$. The Taylor series expansion around the origin of such a function is in the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n, \quad (1)$$

denoted by S , the subclass of A consisting of functions that are univalent in U . Also let $S^*(\alpha)$ and $C(\alpha)$ denote the subclasses of S which are respectively, starlike and convex functions of order α , $0 \leq \alpha < 1$, satisfying

$$S^*(\alpha) = \Re \left\{ \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \right\} > \alpha, \quad (2)$$

and

$$C(\alpha) = \Re \left\{ 1 + \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} \right\} > \alpha. \quad (3)$$

Note that $S^*(0) = S^*$ and $C(0) = C$.

From (2) and (3) we have

$$f(z) \in C(\alpha) \Leftrightarrow zf'(z) \in S^*(\alpha). \quad (4)$$

Denote by T the subclass of A consisting of functions f of the form

$$f(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n. \quad (5)$$

This subclass was introduced and studied by Silverman [11].

Let $T^*(\alpha) = S^*(\alpha) \cap T$ and $K(\alpha) = C(\alpha) \cap T$.

The classes $UCV(\alpha, \sigma)$ consisting of uniform σ -convex functions of order α , and $SP(\alpha, \sigma)$ consisting of parabolic σ -starlike functions of order α , with $-1 < \alpha \leq 1$, $\sigma \geq 0$, are defined by

$$UCV(\alpha, \sigma) := \left\{ f \in \mathcal{A} : \Re \left(1 + \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} - \alpha \right) > \sigma \left| \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} \right|, z \in \mathbb{U} \right\}, \quad (6)$$

EMAIL ADDRESS, P. Srinivasulu: srinivasrgukt1203@gmail.com
EMAIL ADDRESS, V. Srinivas: vsrinivas@braou.ac.in

and

$$SP(\alpha, \sigma) := \left\{ f \in \mathcal{A} : \Re \left(\frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - \alpha \right) > \sigma \left| \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - 1 \right|, z \in \mathbb{U} \right\}. \tag{7}$$

These classes generalize the class UCV and S_p respectively studied by Ronning in [8,9]. See also [2,3,7,15,16].

From (6) and (7) it is obvious that $f \in UCV(\alpha, \sigma)$ if and only if $zf'(z) \in SP(\alpha, \sigma)$.

The following defines the familiar Mittag-Leffler function $E_\nu(z)$ introduced by Mittag-Leffler [5] and its generalization $E_{\nu,\tau}(z)$ introduced by Wiman [17]

$$E_\nu(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\nu n + 1)} \quad \text{and} \quad E_{\nu,\tau}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\nu n + \tau)},$$

where $\nu, \tau \in \mathbb{C}, \Re(\nu) > 0$ and $\Re(\tau) > 0$.

We define the function $Q_{\nu,\tau}(z)$ by

$$Q_{\nu,\tau}(z) = z\Gamma(\tau)E_{\nu,\tau}(z).$$

Now, for $f \in A$, we define the following differential operator $\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f : A \rightarrow A$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{D}_\lambda^0(\nu, \tau)f(z) &= f(z) * Q_{\nu,\tau}(z) \\ \mathfrak{D}_\lambda^1(\nu, \tau)f(z) &= (1 - \lambda)(f(z) * Q_{\nu,\tau}(z)) + \lambda z(f(z) * Q_{\nu,\tau}(z))' \\ &\vdots \\ \mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z) &= \mathfrak{D}_\lambda^1(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^{m-1}(\nu, \tau)f(z)). \end{aligned}$$

If f is given by (1) then from the definition of the operator $\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m f$ it is easy to see that

$$\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_n z^n, \tag{8}$$

where

$$\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) = \frac{\Gamma(\tau)}{\Gamma(\nu(n-1) + \tau)} [\lambda(n-1) + 1]^m. \tag{9}$$

Note that

1. when $\nu = 0$ and $\tau = 1$, we get Al-Oboudi operator [1].
2. when $\nu = 0, \tau = 1$ and $\lambda = 1$, we get Salagean operator [10].
3. when $m = 0$, we get $E_{\nu,\tau}(z)$, Srivastava et al. [14].

If $f \in T$ is given by then we have

$$\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_n z^n.$$

Now, by making use of the differential operator $\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f$, we define a new subclass of functions belonging to the class A .

In this paper, using the operator $\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z)$, we define the following new class motivated by Murugusundaramoorthy and Magesh [6].

Definition 1. The function $f(z)$ of the form (1) is in the class $S_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$ if it satisfies the inequality

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{z(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z))'}{\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z)} - \gamma \right\} > \varsigma \left| \frac{z(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z))'}{\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)f(z)} - 1 \right|,$$

for $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ and $\varsigma \geq 0$.

Further we define $TS_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma) = S_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma) \cap T$.

The purpose of this paper is to study the coefficient bounds, radii of close-to-convex and starlikeness extreme points for the class $TS_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$. In addition, we conclude the paper with integral means inequalities for the functions in $TS_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$.

2 Coefficient Inequalities

In this section, we derive coefficient estimates for the class $TS_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$.

Theorem 1. A function $f(z)$ of the form (1) is in $S_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) |a_n| \leq 1 - \gamma, \tag{10}$$

where $0 \leq \gamma < 1, \varsigma \geq 0$ and $\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)$ is given by (9).

Proof. It suffices to show that

$$\varsigma \left| \frac{z(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z))'}{\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z)} - 1 \right| - \Re \left\{ \frac{z(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z))'}{\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z)} - 1 \right\} \leq 1 - \gamma.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \varsigma \left| \frac{z(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z))'}{\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z)} - 1 \right| - \Re \left\{ \frac{z(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z))'}{\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z)} - 1 \right\} \\ & \leq (1 + \varsigma) \left| \frac{z(\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z))'}{\mathfrak{D}_\lambda^m(\nu, \tau)u(z)} - 1 \right| \\ & \leq (1 + \varsigma) \frac{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n - 1) \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) |a_n| |z|^{n-1}}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) |a_n| |z|^{n-1}} \\ & \leq (1 + \varsigma) \frac{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n - 1) \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) |a_n|}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) |a_n|}. \end{aligned}$$

The last expression is bounded above by $(1 - \gamma)$ if

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) |a_n| \leq 1 - \gamma,$$

and the proof is complete. □

Theorem 2. Let $0 \leq \gamma < 1$ and $\varsigma \geq 0$ then a function f of the form (5) to be in the class $TS_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$ if and only if

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) \leq 1 - \gamma \tag{11}$$

where $\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)$ is given by (9).

Proof. In view of Theorem 1, we need only to prove the necessity. If $f \in TS_\lambda^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$ and z is real then

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_n z^{n-1}}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_n z^{n-1}} - \gamma \right\} > \varsigma \left| \frac{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n - 1) \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_n z^{n-1}}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_n z^{n-1}} \right|.$$

Letting $z \rightarrow 1$ along the real axis, we obtain the desired inequality

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) |a_n| \leq 1 - \gamma,$$

where $0 \leq \gamma < 1, \varsigma \geq 0$ and $\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)$ is given by (9). □

The following corollary is immediate.

Corollary 1. If $f(z) \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$, then

$$|a_n| \leq \frac{1 - \gamma}{[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}, \tag{12}$$

where $0 \leq \gamma < 1$, $\varsigma \geq 0$ and $\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)$ are given by (4). Equality holds for the function

$$f(z) = z - \frac{1 - \gamma}{[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)} z^n. \tag{13}$$

3 Extreme Points

Toward deriving extreme points, we have the following theorem.

Theorem 3. Let $f_1(z) = z$ and

$$f_n(z) = z - \frac{1 - \gamma}{[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)} z^n, n \geq 2. \tag{14}$$

Then $f(z) \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$, if and only if it can be expressed in the form

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} w_n f_n(z), w_n \geq 0, \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} w_n = 1. \tag{15}$$

Proof. Suppose $f(z)$ can be written as in (15). Then

$$f(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} w_n \frac{1 - \gamma}{[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)} z^n.$$

Now,

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} w_n \frac{(1 - \gamma)[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + 1)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(1 - \gamma)[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + 1)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)} = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} w_n = 1 - w_1 \leq 1.$$

Thus $f(z) \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$.

Conversely, let us have $f(z) \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$. Then by using (12), we get

$$w_n = \frac{[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + 1)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(1 - \gamma)} a_n, n \geq 2$$

and $w_1 = 1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} w_n$. Then we have $f(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} w_n f_n(z)$ and hence this completes the proof of Theorem. □

Theorem 4. The class $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$ is a convex set.

Proof. Let $f_j(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_{n,j} z^n$, $a_{n,j} \geq 0$, $j = 1, 2$ be in the class $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$. It is sufficient to show that the function $h(z)$ defined by

$$h(z) = \xi f_1(z) + (1 - \xi) f_2(z), 0 \leq \xi < 1$$

is in the class $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$. Since

$$h(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [\xi a_{n,1} + (1 - \xi) a_{n,2}] z^n.$$

An easy computation with the aid of Theorem 2, gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \xi \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_{n,1} + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] (1 - \xi) \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau) a_{n,2} \\ & \leq \xi(1 - \gamma) + (1 - \xi)(1 - \gamma) \\ & \leq (1 - \gamma), \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $h \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$. Hence $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$ is convex. □

Next we obtain the radii of close-to-convexity and starlikeness for the class $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$.

4 Radii of Close-to-Convexity and Starlikeness

Theorem 5. Let the function $f(z)$ defined by (5) belong to the class $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$. Then $f(z)$ is close-to-convex of order δ ($0 \leq \delta < 1$) in the disc $|z| < r_1$, where

$$r_1 = \inf_{n \geq 2} \left[\frac{(1 - \delta) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{n(1 - \gamma)} \right]^{1/n-1}. \tag{16}$$

The estimate is sharp, with the extremal function $f(z)$ is given by (13).

Proof. Given $f \in T$, and f is close-to-convex of order δ , we have

$$|f'(z) - 1| < 1 - \delta. \tag{17}$$

For the left hand side of (17) we have

$$|f'(z) - 1| \leq \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} na_n |z|^{n-1}.$$

The last expression is less than $1 - \delta$

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{n}{1 - \delta} a_n |z|^{n-1} \leq 1.$$

Using the fact that $f(z) \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \varsigma)$ if and only if

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(1 - \gamma)} a_n \leq 1,$$

then (17) is true if

$$\frac{n}{1 - \delta} |z|^{n-1} \leq \frac{[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(1 - \gamma)}$$

or, equivalently,

$$|z| \leq \left\{ \frac{(1 - \delta)[n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{n(1 - \gamma)} \right\}^{1/n-1}$$

which completes the proof. □

Theorem 6. Let the function $f(z)$ defined by (5) belong to the class $TS_{\lambda}^m(\delta, \gamma, \varsigma)$. Then $f(z)$ is starlike of order δ ($0 \leq \delta < 1$) in the disc $|z| < r_2$, where

$$r_2 = \inf_{n \geq 2} \left[\frac{(1 - \delta) \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n(1 + \varsigma) - (\gamma + \varsigma)] \phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(n - \delta)(1 - \gamma)} \right]^{1/n-1}. \tag{18}$$

The estimate is sharp, with extremal function $f(z)$ is given by (13).

Proof. Given $f \in T$, and f is starlike of order δ , we have

$$\left| \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - 1 \right| < 1 - \delta. \tag{19}$$

For the left hand side of (19) we have

$$\left| \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - 1 \right| \leq \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(n - 1)a_n |z|^{n-1}}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n |z|^{n-1}}.$$

The last expression is less than $1 - \delta$ if

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{n - \delta}{1 - \delta} a_n |z|^{n-1} < 1.$$

Using the fact that $f(z) \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \zeta)$ if and only if

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{[n(1 + \zeta) - (\gamma + \zeta)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(1 - \gamma)} a_n \leq 1,$$

we can say (19) is true if

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{n - \delta}{1 - \delta} |z|^{n-1} \leq \frac{[n(1 + \zeta) - (\gamma + \zeta)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(1 - \gamma)}$$

or equivalently

$$|z|^{n-1} \leq \frac{(1 - \delta)[n(1 + \zeta) - (\gamma + \zeta)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)}{(n - \delta)(1 - \gamma)}$$

which yields the starlikeness of the family. □

5 Integral Means Inequalities

In [13], Silverman found that the function $f_2(z) = z - \frac{z^2}{2}$ is often extremal over the family T . This function was used to solve his integral means inequality, which was conjectured in [12] and settled in [13], that

$$\int_0^{2\pi} |f(re^{i\phi})|^n d\phi \leq \int_0^{2\pi} |f_2(re^{i\phi})|^n d\phi,$$

for all $f \in T, n > 0$ and $0 < r < 1$. In [13], he also proved his conjuncture for the subclasses $T^*(\alpha)$ and $C(\alpha)$ of T .

For the class of functions $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \zeta)$, we next aim to prove Silverman’s conjecture.

Littlewood’s subordination theorem [4] and the concept of subordination between analytic functions are required.

For two functions f and g , which are analytic in U , the function f is said to be subordinate to g in U if there exists a function w analytic in U with $w(0) = 0, |w(z)| < 1, (z \in U)$ Such that $f(z) = g(w(z)), (z \in U)$. We denote this subordination by $f(z) \prec g(z)$ (\prec denotes subordination).

Lemma 1. *If the functions f and g are analytic in U with $f(z) \prec g(z)$, then for $n > 0$ and $z = re^{i\phi} 0 < r < 1$,*

$$\int_0^{2\pi} |f(re^{i\phi})|^n d\phi \leq \int_0^{2\pi} |g(re^{i\phi})|^n d\phi.$$

Now, we discuss the integral means inequalities for functions f in $TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \zeta)$.

Theorem 7. *Let $f \in TS_{\lambda}^m(\gamma, \zeta), 0 \leq \gamma < 1$, and $f_2(z)$ be specified by*

$$f_2(z) = z - \frac{1 - \gamma}{\phi_2(\lambda, m, \zeta, \gamma)} z^2. \tag{20}$$

Then for $z = re^{i\phi}$ we have, $\int_0^{2\pi} |f(z)|^n d\phi \leq \int_0^{2\pi} |f_2(z)|^n d\phi$.

Proof. For $f(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n$, (20) is equivalent to

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \left| 1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^{n-1} \right|^n d\phi \leq \int_0^{2\pi} \left| 1 - \frac{1 - \gamma}{\phi_2(\lambda, m, \zeta, \gamma)} z \right|^n d\phi.$$

By Lemma 1, it is enough to prove that

$$1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^{n-1} \prec 1 - \frac{1 - \gamma}{\phi_2(\lambda, m, \zeta, \gamma)} z.$$

Assuming

$$1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^{n-1} \prec 1 - \frac{1 - \gamma}{\phi_2(\lambda, m, \zeta, \gamma)} w(z),$$

and using (11) we obtain

$$|w(z)| = \left| \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\phi_2(\lambda, m, \zeta, \gamma)}{1 - \gamma} a_n z^{n-1} \right| \leq |z| \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\phi_2(\lambda, m, \zeta, \gamma)}{1 - \gamma} a_n \leq |z|$$

where $\phi_n(\lambda, m, \zeta, \gamma) = [n(1 + \zeta) - (\gamma + \zeta)]\phi_n^m(\lambda, \nu, \tau)$, which completes the proof. □

6 Conclusion

This study considered some basic properties of the geometric function theory and established a new subclass of univalent functions defined by Mittag-Leffler functions with negative coefficients. Consequently, some coefficient estimates, radii of starlike and close-to-convexity, extreme points, and other results have been investigated, paving the way for further research in the subject.

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Competing Interests

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